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Characterization of transcriptional properties of the E7 protein of human papillomavirus type 42 (HPV42), a low-risk HPV with oncogenic potential.

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We measured total transcription in cells expressing the E7 protein of low-risk HPV42, a low-risk HPV type with oncogenic potential. Expression of HPV42 E7 resulted in mixed proliferative phenotype characterized by activation of PCNA and nucleotide synthesis enzymes TYMS and TK1, with activation of CDKN1A but silencing of CDK6. HPV42 E7 altered EMT program expression with silencing of vimentin. The E7 protein of a low-risk papillomavirus could this finely modulate cell cycle dynamics and processes important for transformation and invasive behavior.